

Walk the Yorke Map Assessment - General

If you are part of the Yorke Peninsula Council, another organization with direct links to the trail, or have specific knowledge in the areas of digital cartography/GIS, tourism, or trail management please fill out [this survey instead](#).

We have been developing a web map of the Walk the Yorke Trail and would love your feedback! Our map is intended to be useful and usable for all trail users. It also includes functions allowing you to add comments, reviews, and share points with other trail users and for the benefit of trail managers. We would appreciate your feedback on how easy the map is to use and how effectively the design and functionality of the map meets your needs. The map is still at the prototype stage so please accept that there will be a few bugs, and that trail information is incomplete. The map can be found at <https://wtj.joshgore.com.au/>.

This project has been approved by the University of South Australia's Human Research Ethics Committee. Please read the [Participant Information Sheet](#). By completing and submitting the survey, you are indicating that you have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet and give your consent to be involved in the research.

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About You

1. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Year 11 or below
- Year 12
- Technical or Trade Qualification
- Bachelor degree - in progress
- Bachelor degree
- Postgraduate degree (Masters or higher)
- Prefer not to say

2. Your Age

- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65+

3. Where do you live?

- Yorke Peninsula
- South Australia
- Other Australia
- Outside Australia

4. How familiar are you with the Walk the Yorke Trail?

Not at all Familiar

Very Familiar

A horizontal scale with five radio buttons, evenly spaced, used for selecting a familiarity level. The scale is contained within a light gray rectangular bar.

5. Which of the following best describes your preferred trail usage (i.e. which one of these usages are your answers most relevant too?)

- Casual Walker (short walks up to 7km)
- Half Day Walker (up to 15km)
- Long Day Walker (15km+)
- Overnight Hiker
- Casual Cyclist (<20km)
- Long Distance Cyclist (>20km)

6. Please rate your technical knowledge about digital maps

Very Low

Very High

7. Please rate your ability to adapt to new software

Very Low

Very High

8. Which browser are you using to view the map?

- Chrome
- Firefox
- Edge
- Safari
- Internet Explorer (will not work)
- Other (please specify)

9. You may conduct this survey whilst viewing the map on one or several different devices. Which devices are you viewing the map on?

- Desktop
- Laptop
- High end smartphone
- mid-range smartphone
- low end smartphone
- high end tablet
- mid-range tablet
- low-end tablet

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Map Design

Task 1. View a description of a trail section.

10. How easy was this task to complete?

Very Hard

Very Easy

11. How useful was the information layout?

Not at all Useful

Very Useful

12. Any Comments?

Task 2. View information associated with a trail shelter.

13. Was it clear that you could click on the points to gain additional information?

Not at all Clear

Very Clear

14. Any comments?

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Map Interaction

Task 3. View comments and reviews associated with a stage and submit a review (create an account or use test1234 for username and password)

15. How easy was this task to complete?

Very Hard

Very Easy

16. How useful do you think reviews will be for trail users?

Not at all Useful

Very Useful

17. How useful do you think comments will be for trail users?

Not at all Useful

Very Useful

18. Any Comments?

Task 4. Add a point to the map (create an account or use test1234 for username and password)

19. How easy was this task to complete?

Very Hard

Very Easy

20. How useful do you think this feature will be to trail users?

Not at all Useful

Very Useful

21. Any comments?

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General Questions

22. Overall, how would you rate the experience of using this map?

Very Unpleasant

Very Pleasant

23. Overall, how would you rate the design of this map?

Very Poor

Very Good

24. Rate your agreement with the following on a scale of one to ten

Strongly
Disagree

Strongly
Agree

I think I would like to use the Walk the Yorke web map when planning my trail use

I thought the web map was easy to use

I thought the various functions in the web map were well integrated

I would imagine that most people would learn to use the web map very quickly

25. Do you have any general comments on the map?

26. Are there any functions we should add to the map?

27. Please provide your email address if you would like a one-page summary of the research findings emailed to you (this will occur in early December).

Email Address

Thanks for your time!

